

Seed Characterization and Dormancy Breaking of *Terminalia laxiflora* Engl. and Diels

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Abstract

Terminalia laxiflora is one of the important Sudanese forest trees that used for railway sleepers, firewood, fumigants and medicinal uses. This species is expected to disappear due to its low germination percentage (0-5 %). This study was aimed to test the best pre-treatment that suitable for breaking its dormancy. The pre-treatments applied were soaking in water (24, 48, 72, 96,120,144,168 hours), soaking in boiling water (1, 3 minutes and 24 hours) and soaking in acid (30, 45, 60 minutes). The results showed that the best pre treatment was soaking in sulfuric acid for 60 min, it gave 55 % .This result with relation to high percentage of dead seeds seems to raise the germination percentage to 100%.

Key words: Dormancy, Viability, Pre- treatment

Introduction

Terminalia laxiflora tree is up to 12 m high. Bark dark grey, deeply fissured, branches grey to brown. Leaves simple spirally arranged closely alternate at the ends of the twig. Flowers white. Fruits oblong to oblong-elliptic. Flowering: Feb.-May; Fruit: March-Oct (Ismail

2007). It is grown on loamy soils in high rainfall savannah. In Sudan it is found in Darfur, South Kordofan (Jebel Dair, Nuba Mts, South Blue Nile, ElGadarif, Upper Nile, Bahr El-Ghazal and Equatoria. Seed dormancy refers to a state in which viable seeds fail to germinate when provided with conditions normally favorable to germination i.e. adequate moisture, appropriate temperature regime, a normal atmosphere and in some cases light. Dormancy has evolved as a strategy to avoid germination under conditions where seedling survival is likely to be low (Willan 1985). There are various degrees of dormancy varying from very slight to very strong or deep. Sometimes the development or degree of dormancy changes during the lifetime of the seed, usually as a response to external conditions (Willan, 1992). Dormancy in seeds may be an advantageous or problematic during seed handling. The advantage is that it prevents seeds from germinating during storage and other handling procedures, and induction of dormancy by drying and dark storage generally promotes storability. On the other hand, where dormancy is complex and seeds need a very specific pretreatment, failure to overcome these problems may result in very poor germination (Willan, 1985). Therefore the main purpose of pretreatment is to ensure both that seeds will germinate, and the germination is fast and uniform. Terminalia spp is a common indigenous species in wood land and semi humid Savannah of the Sudan. It is a useful multipurpose species with a high potential of timber production and medicinal uses. From previous studies (Mohammed, 2002) the poor germination of seeds is

found to be an obstacle for plantation of forest tree species. Poor germination was found to be partly due to the combined dormancy chemical, mechanical and indigenous causes. So this study was carried out to explore the appropriate pre- treatment to solve dormancy problem of this species.

Materials and Methods

Fruits of *Terminalia laxiflora* were collected from ElNour forest east of Eldamazin city at Blue Nile state in season 2007. Random samples were drawn from the working samples and the following test was applied as described in (International Seed Testing Association) ISTA rules 1993 for each test: seed cutting test to test viability, Number of seed/ kg, Moisture content, purity test and 14 different pre-treatments.

In Control pre- treatment the fruits were sown without any treatment, Soaking in water for (24,48, 72, 96, 120, 144, 168) hours, Soaking in hot water seeds were soaked in 4-5 times their size boiled water for (1,3 minute and 24 hours) and washed immediately. Soaking in sulphuric acid (commercial acid 98%) for (15, 30, 45 and 60) minutes, stirring with a glass rod during the soaking period. after soaking, the seeds were washed with water for 10 minutes. For each pre- treatment 100 fruits were used. These fruits were divided into 4 replicates of 25 fruits each. Fruitss were sown immediately after treatment. Fruits were sown in round aluminium dishes filled with moist sand. Dishes were watered daily with a fine shower. Germination was carried out in a controlled germination room at the National Tree Seed Centre –Soba

30°C, light for 12 hours from fluorescent lamps. Germination counts were done at 7 days interval and for a period of 6 weeks. The CRD (Complete Randomize Design) with four replicates was selected and the statistical analysis was done by JMP package (Programme improved form SAS Package)

Results and discussion

The results of *Terminalia laxiflora* trees showed that its fruits purity were about 92 % and 81% respectively (table, 1), this test was designed to show the odd material in the collected bulk beside the seeds of the target species. Its Moisture content about 4.4 (table, 1), this percentage is usually a character of seeds of good storability and a higher response to low temperature storage (Schmidt, 2000). Although Mohammed, 2002 found that storing *T. laxiflora* fruits at room temperature was better than storing at cool storage.

Table 1. Characteristics of *Terminalia laxiflora* fruits

Purity %	No of seeds/kg (1000)	Moisture content %	Viability%
92	3.611	4.4	72

The seed cutting test results as indicator of the fruits viability showed about 72 % for *T. laxiflora* (table, 2). The cutting test gives important information about the seed lot; it shows the status of the seed lot.

Table 2. The differences in fruits viability between *Terminalia laxiflora* 10 trees using cutting test method

Trees	Sound fruits %	Empty fruits %	Dead fruits%
Tree1	2	0	98
Tree2	36	0	64
Tree3	14	0	86
Tree4	10	0	90
Tree5	30	0	70
Tree6	58	0	42
Tree7	54	0	46
Tree8	74	0	26
Tree9	70	0	30
Tree10	24	0	76
Mean	38,4	0	61.6

Terminalia laxiflora has very low germination percentage which was an obstacle problem facing re-forestation programmes. While the result of sowing *T. Laxiflora* fruits without any treatments gave about 19% germination (Table 2.4) other studies on the same species had about 9.5 % (Mohammed, 2002). This problem was found to exist among most members of the family Combretaceae such as *T. brownii* 0% and *Anogiosus leocarpus* 2.5 % germination (Mohammed, 2002). The seed cutting test of *Terminalia laxiflora* for the ten trees showed a high percentage of dead seeds and this percentage vary from one tree

to another (Table 2). Most of the dead seeds were found to be damaged by insect; from 98% dead seed in tree No 1 to 26% tree No 8, this finding may be an indicator for variation of seeds chemical content in the same species, which possibly made some fruits more favourable for insect than other fruits. The variation of secondary metabolic within species was recorded by Kelman (1999) in *Parerythropodium fulvum fulvum* which its major metabolite in the yellow morph, varied considerably among samples. This finding agreed with Yamego and Some (1993) work *T. aviceenniodes* that the cause of poor germination was the presence of a very hard endocarp and a very high rate of insect damage. Trees which produced high nutritive seed, it was found that some of the seed were attacked with higher rate, and some that are not attacked, might have a component that is not desirable for insects to feed on. With this high percentage of dead seeds we can't expect a high percentage of germinations and these results may explain the variation in result for the different lots of the same species from the same population (Elnour forest). The freshly collected seeds in the same year when subjected to germination tests; seeds germinated in the bulk sample were 37% which is a very low percentage of germination.

The different treatments of the *Terminalia laxiflora* seeds gave good results (Table 3) especially when the seeds were treated with Sulphuric acid for an hour which gave about 55%, this percentage indicated that all sound and viable seeds were germinated Okunlola *etal* (2011) reported that the pre-treatment with sulfuric acid raised the germination percentage significantly in *Parkia biglobsa* While the

same pre- treatment give poor germination percentage in *Terminalia sericea*. This may be a high germination percentage (55%) because all the sound seeds (37%) were germinated so it can considered as 100% of germination.

The acid treatment was found to be the best because it works in two directions, softening the fleshy coat of the seeds and leaching the inhibitors that may exist in the coat and pulp of the fruit., while soaking in tap water for different times (24, 48, 72, 96,120,144 and 168 hours) didn't give a different result from the control. But the control gave about 50% germination comparable to 37% sound seeds (Table 3).

These differences need a lot of work in different way, studies on nutritive value of seeds of *Terminalia laxiflora* from different trees and if there are any differences between trees with it may reflect on insect damage. Or the high percentage of infestation due to environmental factors.

Table 3. Effect of different treatments on *Terminalia laxiflora* germination percentage

Treatments	Mean %	Rank
Control	19.1	cde
Soaking in water 24 hours	16.4	cdef
Soaking in water 48 hours	10.8	cdef
Soaking in water 72 hours	16.2	cdef
Soaking in water 96 hours	14.5	defg
Soaking in water 120 hours	4.1	g
Soaking in water 144 hours	25.8	c
Soaking in water 168 hours	22.1	cd
Soaking in boiling water 1 minute	5.9	fg
Soaking in boiling water 3 minute	21.7	cd
Soaking in boiling water 24 hours	42.1	b
Soaking in Acid 15 minute	11.7	defg
Soaking in Acid 30 minute	37.8	b
Soaking in Acid 45 minute	52.1	ab
Soaking in Acid 60 minute	55.1	a

$p \leq 0.0001$

SE± 3.6

CV=20

Conclusion

The best pre treatment for *T.laxiflora* was soaking in acid for 60 minutes, which raised the germination percentage to 55.1.

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